

TEACHING MODERN FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7749164>

Otaboyeva Oymonjon Jaloladdin qizi

Urganch State Pedagogical Institute

1st year student in foreign language and literature (English)

Annotation: This article explores the issues of using modern technologies of the global Internet, as well as their interaction with traditional methods in the process of learning and teaching foreign languages.

Keywords: ICT, and a foreign language, interactive learning, multimedia tools.

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is a turbulent time characterized by unprecedented global changes and transformations. The achievements of science and the development of technologies every year acquire more perfect forms, giving a new impetus to thought processes as new opportunities and means appear for transforming and connecting the external awareness of the surrounding reality with the internal processes of mental activity. As we enter the age of digital and information and communication technologies, we are faced with tasks of a kind that we have never encountered before. School and university teachers around the world are trying to keep up with technical and technological progress, but in order to prepare students for life in the 21st century, it is necessary to reconsider the entire education system as a whole, and take a fresh look at teaching methods. To optimize and achieve maximum efficiency of the educational process, it is necessary to clearly understand the true needs of students of the 21st century, namely¹:

¹ Information system "Single window of access to educational resources" // FGU GNII ITT "Informika" - 2015 - 2011 [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <http://window.edu.ru/window/about>

- effectively communicate information, thoughts and feelings to other people
- be creative in solving emerging problems and issues
- actively interact with other people
- Critically think, compare and analyze.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

At the present stage of technology development, all interactive methods for optimizing the assimilation of material in the process of teaching foreign languages can be classified according to the way they are introduced into the educational process and according to the goals that need to be achieved when using a particular method. The practical use of interactive methods that can be applied in the process of teaching foreign languages can be divided into two groups:

- working offline, that is, not requiring a connection to the global Internet: interactive whiteboards and CDs

- working online, that is, requiring connection to the global Internet: network resources in the form of various educational and developmental exercises, games, images, videos on the websites of well-known publishers and organizations (Cambridge, Oxford, Macmillan, British Council, etc.), and interactive test systems².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

These funds undoubtedly mark a qualitatively new stage in the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages. So, let's consider each of the above multimedia tools and technologies separately. At the moment, more and more foreign language teachers use in their work, in addition to traditional methods and techniques, countless innovations offered by the world of computer technology, and, in particular, interactive whiteboards.

But what exactly are interactive whiteboards? There are two types of such multimedia tools: virtual and real interactive whiteboards. A virtual whiteboard is a

² Burimskaya DV - Higher Schools on the Way to the Bologna Process. // Foreign languages: theory and practice. - 2010. - No. 1. – pp. 21-23

regular chalkboard placed on a computer monitor, which helps students in the online space of a class or audience to see everything that the teacher writes or depicts on the screen. Such a whiteboard is also called an electronic whiteboard, it is usually used at conferences, presentations or in data sharing systems when organizing audio and video contacts between two or more participants using programs such as Microsoft NetMeeting, Microsoft Office Live Meeting. A real interactive whiteboard is seen as a large monitor panel that combines the functions of an ordinary chalkboard, a projector screen, an electronic copy of the whiteboard and a computer touch monitor. In turn, real interactive whiteboards are divided into four subspecies, depending on the technologies used: resistive (touch), electromagnetic, ultrasonic (infrared) and laser³. The capabilities of these interactive whiteboards allow you to create a wide range of educational programs that become indispensable for both teachers and students in the process of studying foreign language material. Today, there are a wide variety of companies involved in the development of such multimedia tools: Smart Technologies, Egan TeamBoard, GTCO CalComp, Promethean, ReturnStar, PolyVision, Hitachi, Panasonic, Interactive Technologies, etc., and the most common software for boards of this kind today remains Microsoft Office Word and PowerPoint.

In recent years, a significant number of interactive CDs have appeared, both stand-alone, containing programs, dictionaries and foreign language courses, and included in modern educational and methodological complexes in the form of supplements to the "Book for the teacher", "Book for the student" and "Workbook". The multimedia basis of educational CDs allows presenting the studied material simultaneously in text, graphic, sound and visual forms. In the process of combining various audiovisual sources of information in an emotional-figurative context, various types of memory and thinking are activated, increasing the overall effectiveness and efficiency of mastering the studied material. Modeling of

³ Pakhomenko V.E. IWB. Let's figure it out! // Britannia Millennium - 2019 - 23 September [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: http://www.elit-zone.ru/resources/articles/3076/art_14639.html

communicative situations with the help of certain programs on disks immerses students in the socio-cultural atmosphere of foreign language communication. Interactive CDs act as excellent media for disseminating the necessary information and at the same time do not require connection to the global Internet, providing the ability to view data anywhere and anytime. Such electronic learning tools can be used as additional material in foreign language classes when consolidating and monitoring the acquired knowledge and skills, programs for self-education, as well as to avoid problems of "lag" among students absent from classes. In other words, if students miss this or that material, the interactive disk, which is part of the teaching materials and includes sections such as a summary guide to grammar, vocabulary, audio and video files with texts and pronunciation norms of lexical units, helps to compensate and minimize problems "backlog", because it gives students certain tools for self-working out the missed material. Taking one of the newest educational courses published by Cambridge publishers, Face2Face, the interactive CD that comes with this tutorial provides students with the following range of activities:

- the use and development of the studied material on more than 200 types of exercises
- reading and listening (with or without support) of the main audio recordings from the Student's Book
- using the "achievements" function to display the percentage of correctly completed tasks for each exercise, lesson or course as a whole and print this data
- students creating their own exercises or lessons using the provided materials
- students compiling their own tests from 600 proposed tasks⁴.

Today, many educational institutions include in their plans and programs preparation for passing official international exams (English: KET, PET, FCE, ESOL, BEC, CAE, CPE, IELTS, TOEFL, TOEIC, etc.; French : DALF, DELF, TEF, CEFP, etc.; German: TestDaF, TDN, DSH, ZD, ZMP, etc.; Spanish: DELE,

⁴ Ch. Redston, R. Clark, A. Young, H. Coward with G. Cunningham. – Face2Face Pre-Intermediate. teacher's book. Cambridge University Press, 4th printing 2019.

CIE, DBE, DSE, etc.), the results of which are considered the most reliable and objective indicator of the level of foreign language proficiency.

CONCLUSION

So, we can conclude that in the age of computer technology and the heyday of the global Internet, it is very important to find the right and optimal combination, ratio, the golden mean between interactive, multimedia tools and technologies of the global Internet and traditional methods of teaching foreign languages in order to create favorable conditions for students, influencing the formation and maintenance of their motivation to learn a foreign language and to reveal, expand students' opportunities to work with information, which contributes to the development of their innovative thinking, enhances the desire for collective learning in cooperation, forms language and communicative competence.

REFERENCES

1. Burimskaya DV - Higher Schools on the Way to the Bologna Process. // Foreign languages: theory and practice. - 2010. - No. 1. – pp. 21-23
2. Information system "Single window of access to educational resources" // FGU GNII ITT "Informika" - 2015 - 2011 [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <http://window.edu.ru/window/about>
3. Pakhomenko V.E. IWB. Let's figure it out! // Britannia Millennium - 2019 - 23 September [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: http://www.elt-zone.ru/resources/articles/3076/art_14639.html
4. Ch. Redston, R. Clark, A. Young, H. Coward with G. Cunningham. – Face2Face Pre-Intermediate. teacher's book. Cambridge University Press, 4th printing 2019.
5. Ch. Redston, R. Clark, A. Young, H. Coward with G. Cunningham. – Face2Face Pre-Intermediate. Student's Book with CD Rom. Cambridge University Press, 4th printing 2019.
- 6 Council of Europe. Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment. Cambridge University Press, 2001.

7. K.Flach, S.Mclood, J.Bronman. Education And The Future of Technology
// YouTube - 2109– April 7 [Electronic resource]. – Access mode:
http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vPO_HGafBsE